

Editorial

Sixth issue of the European Journal of Philosophy in Arts Education

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Editor in Chief

The second and last EJPAE issue of 2019 is finally due – in 2020. Running a journal is interesting since there are many parameters that are out of the editor's control – such as when reviewers return reviews, when authors return their revisions and so on. And since this journal is run voluntarily, the typesetting and finalising have to fit into my schedule at university. Sometimes this is frustrating, but everyone is gentle and patient, and when I see the great result, such and in this issue, I feel really proud!

The issue starts off with an amazing article by **Juvas Marianne Liljas** about a Swedish reform school, the Siljan School in Tällberg, based on the ideals of the Swedish pedagogue Ellen Key. The article is unusually empirical for EJPAE, but uses the empirical data theoretically to discuss aesthetic schooling in an early nineteenth century rural setting. The education offered in this was an alternative to a more modernistic and mechanical education, and in the Siljan School the child's needs were in focus and hence the arts were important ingredients in how the school was run. The article is illustrated with photography from the school which gives a strong sense of being in the milieu where the education took place.

The second article deals with the complex issues concerning the ethics involved in performing research in a school environment. The Finnish researchers **Cecilia Björk** and **Marja-Leena Juntunen** investigate what virtue ethics can offer researchers in music education and suggest solutions to ethical challenges that are relational and relative to each situation. In an approach critical of a rules and laws based practice of choosing a safe way out of possible ethical issues, they choose a completely different path. Instead of depending on predetermined solutions, researchers should make use of practical wisdom with deep respect for all involved parties and the research. The article should be read by all who do empirical research as it provides a framework to think about many different aspects of the ethics of performing research in a school environment, and how to develop the virtues necessary to become an ethical researcher.

Also on the topic of suggesting a new framework for thinking, the third and last article deals with music as a revolutionary tool in society. The Greek researcher **Alexandros Kioupiolis** suggests a new paradigm for thinking about music education as a vehicle for social change. Kioupiolis uses the concept of *the commons* to create a framework of collaborative action where autonomous creation and equality – both creatively and regarding ownership. To do this he goes through the history of the commons and current practices of the commons to suggest how music education can benefit from similar ideas. The presented ideas challenge current ideologies of authorship and copyright that were not designed for a public education in the first place. To delve into this article is to enter a possible world of a joyous and unpretentious education that fosters happy, creative and skilled citizens – in the arts and in general.

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